

Synthesis and Biological Activity of some New 6-Thiophene-7H-indeno[2,1-c]quinolines

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6-Thienyl-7H-indeno[2,1-c]quinoline and its 2,3- and 4-methoxy analogues (4a-d) have been synthesised by the condensation of 2-thienoylindan-1,3-dione (1) with aniline and three isomeric anisidines, followed by cyclodehydration with polyphosphoric acid and Wolff-Kishner reduction. The structures of all the products have been established by elemental analysis and spectral data.

AZFLUORENES and their benzanalogues (indenoquinolines) are reported to possess varied biological activity¹⁻³. Recently some indenoquinolines were reported to exhibit significant analgesic and anti-inflammatory activities⁴. In view of these reports and in continuation of our work⁵, we report the synthesis of some new 6-thienyl-7H-indeno[2,1-c]quinoline and its 2,3- and 4-methoxy analogues (4a-d) through a convenient route (Scheme 1).

- 2-4 a; R₁^a = R₂ = R₃ = H
 b; R₁ = OCH₃, R₂ = R₃ = H
 c; R₂ = OCH₃, R₁ = R₃ = H
 d; R₃ = OCH₃, R₁ = R₂ = H

Scheme 1

Results and Discussion

Condensation of 2-thienoylindan-1,3-dione (1)⁶ with aniline and isomeric anisidines in refluxing ethanol gave the corresponding anils (2a-d) in excellent yields, $\nu_{\max}$ 1695-1690 (C=O) and 1635-1630 cm⁻¹ (C=N); pmr δ 12.10-12.15 (exchangeable with D₂O, enolic H).

The anils (2) on treatment with PPA at 180° yielded the corresponding 6-thienylindeno[2,1-c]quinolin-7(H)-ones (3a-d), $\nu_{\max}$ 1705-1700 cm⁻¹ (C=O). A noteworthy feature of these ketones is that pmr chemical shifts of bay protons H-1 and H-11 are significantly deshielded possibly due to steric interaction. The most downfield signal has been assigned to H-1. Similarly situated proton in 7H-benzo[c]fluorene⁷ and 6-phenylindenoquinolin-7(H)-ones⁸ are reported to be more deshielded than H-11. This fact is further supported from the pmr spectra of the ketones (3c and 3d), which exhibited one-proton doublet at δ 8.20 (*J* 8 Hz) and 8.22 (*J* 8 and 2.5 Hz) respectively, attributed to H-1.

The ketones (3a-d) on Wolff-Kishner reduction afforded the desired 6-thiophene-7H-indeno[2,1-c]quinolines (4a-d). These compounds did not display and absorption in the carbonyl region. The pmr spectra of these compounds showed singlet of 2H intensity at δ 4.15 attributed to C(7)-H₂ group; H-1 and H-11 appeared downfield spread at δ 8.20-8.26.

Physical and spectral data of compounds are given in Table 1.

Biological activity: Compounds 2-4 were screened for their general pharmacological activity. LD₅₀ of these compounds was found to be >1000

TABLE 1 - PHYSICAL AND PMR SPECTRAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS*

Compd. no.	M.p. °C	Yield %	Mol. formula	δ (ppm)
2a	176	86	C ₂₀ H ₁₂ NO ₂ S	6.70-7.05 (5H, m, H-2', H-3', H-4', H-5' and H-6'), 7.20-7.70 (7H, m, ArH), 12.20 (1H, br, enolic exchangeable with D ₂ O)
2b	199	82	C ₂₁ H ₁₂ NO ₂ S	3.71 (3H, s, OCH ₃), 6.66 (2H, d, J 8 Hz, H-2' and H-6'), 6.90 (2H, d, J 8 Hz, H-3' and H-5'), 7.14-7.51 (7H, m, ArH), 12.20 (1H, br, H-3 enolic exchangeable)
2c	182	80	C ₂₁ H ₁₂ NO ₂ S	3.72 (3H, s, OCH ₃), 6.55-7.10 (4H, m, H-2', H-4', H-5' and H-6'), 7.24-7.75 (7H, m, ArH), 12.20 (1H, br, H-3 enolic exchangeabl.)
2d	178	85	C ₂₁ H ₁₂ NO ₂ S	3.72 (3H, s, OCH ₃), 6.62-7.10 (4H, m, H-3', H-4', H-5' and H-6'), 7.25-7.65 (7H, m, ArH), 12.20 (1H, br, H-3 enolic exchangeable)
3a	192	40	C ₂₀ H ₁₁ NOS	7.00-7.76 (8H, m, ArH), 7.95-8.05 (2H, m, H-4 and H-11), 8.22 (1H, dd, J 8 and 2.5 Hz, H-1)
3b	205	52	C ₂₁ H ₁₁ NO ₂ S	3.82 (3H, s, OCH ₃), 6.90-7.75 (7H, m, ArH), 7.90-8.15 (3H, m, H-4, H-11 and H-1)
3c	212	42	C ₂₁ H ₁₁ NO ₂ S	3.82 (3H, s, OCH ₃), 7.00-7.80 (8H, m, ArH), 8.00 (1H, dd, J 8 and 2.5 Hz), 8.20 (1H, d, J 8 Hz, H-1)
3d	232	55	C ₂₁ H ₁₁ NO ₂ S	3.84 (3H, s, OCH ₃), 7.00-7.82 (8H, m, ArH), 8.05 (1H, dd, J 8 and 2.5 Hz, H-11), 8.22 (1H, dd, J 8 and 2.5 Hz, H-1)
4a	136	45	C ₂₀ H ₁₁ NS	4.15 (2H, s, CH ₂), 6.92-7.78 (8H, m, ArH), 7.95-8.15 (3H, m, H-4, H-11 and H-1)
4b	144	50	C ₂₁ H ₁₁ NOS	3.78 (3H, s, OCH ₃), 4.15 (2H, s, CH ₂), 7.00-7.90 (9H, m, ArH), 8.24 (1H, d, J 2.5 Hz, H-1)
4c	138	42	C ₂₁ H ₁₁ NOS	3.80 (3H, s, OCH ₃), 4.12 (2H, s, CH ₂), 7.05-7.88 (8H, m, ArH), 8.00 (1H, dd, J 8 and 2.5 Hz, H-11), 8.20 (1H, d, J 8 Hz, H-1)
4d	150	48	C ₂₁ H ₁₁ NOS	3.82 (3H, s, OCH ₃), 4.12 (2H, s, CH ₂), 7.10-8.10 (9H, m, ArH), 8.26 (1H, dd, J 8 and 2.5 Hz, H-1)

*All compounds gave satisfactory C and S analyses.

mg/kg. The compounds did not show any significant CNS and CVS activity in gross observation test. However 3a-d showed noticeable anti-inflammatory activity, i.e. 39, 42, 40 and 41% inhibition respectively at doze level of 100 mg/kg, as compared with phenylbutazone which showed 60% inhibition. The activity was tested by carragenin induced rat paw oedema test⁸.

Experimental

All the melting points were determined in open capillaries and are uncorrected. Ir spectra (nujol) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 783 spectrophotometer, pmr spectra (CDCl₃) on a Jeol FX 900 (90 MHz) spectrometer using TMS as internal standard.

α -(1,3-Dioxindan-2-yl)thienylindeneanilines (2) : A mixture of 2-thienoylindan-1,3-dione (1; 0.001 mol) and appropriate anilines (0.0013 mol) was

refluxed in ethanol (50 ml) for 10 h in presence of a few drops of acetic acid. The solvent was then distilled off and the residue was crystallised from ethanol to get green needles (2a-d).

6-Thiopheneindeno[2,1-c]quinolin-7(H)-7-ones (3) : The anil (2; 0.003 mol) was added to freshly prepared PPA and heated to 180° for 1 h. The reaction mixture was then decomposed by ice-cold water and made alkaline with NH₄OH. The resulting solid was washed with water and crystallised from benzene to yield shining yellow-orange needles (3a-d).

6-Thiophene-7H-indeno[2,1-c]quinollines (4) : A mixture containing ketone (3; 0.001 mol), ethylene glycol (10 ml), hydrazine hydrate (2 ml) was heated to 120° for 1 h and then at 180° for 4 h. The reaction mixture was then poured into ice-cold water. The resulting solid was washed with water, dried

and crystallised from methanol - pyridine mixture to get colourless needles (4a - d).

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